

NATIONAL WILDLIFE HEALTH CENTER

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DIAGNOSTIC SERVICES CASE REPORT

Case: 29037

Final Report

3/8/2019

Epizoo:

Legal Declassified INV#:

Submitter:

Paul Crump
Texas Parks & Wildlife/Austin
4200 Smith School Road
Austin, TX 78744

Date Submitted: 2/13/2019

Specimen description/Identification/Location:

ACC	SPECIES	SPECIMEN TYPE	BAND NUMBER	SUBMITTER'S ID	COUNTY	STATE
001	Snake, Water, Broad-banded	CARCASS			Montgomery	TX

Diagnosis:

Snake Fungal Disease
Emaciation
Mild nematode infestation, caudal esophagus/stomach

Event History:

One broad-banded water snake was collected from the wild with putative SFD symptoms on 01/26/2019 and was held in captivity in isolation for monitoring until it died on 02/04/2019. It has been frozen since it died. This snake is being submitted as part of an ongoing project/collaboration between USGS NWHC and TPWD under TPWD contract # 515403 and USGS agreement # 19NCCOLL00559.

Comment:

This adult Broad-banded Water Snake was emaciated. The snake tested positive for *Ophidiomyces ophiodiicola*, the fungus that causes Snake Fungal Disease, and the laboratory diagnosis was confirmed by the finding of fungal infection characteristic of the disease on histopathology. The only other significant abnormality present in this snake was nematode infestation of the wall of the caudal esophagus and proximal stomach. Only a few migrating nematode larvae were seen, however they did cause tissue damage and inflammation where present.

Wildlife and Domestic Animal Significance: Snake Fungal Disease (SFD) is a newly-described deep fungal infection of snakes. Investigations are underway to determine whether the fungus *Ophidiomyces ophiodiicola* is the sole cause of SFD or whether it is caused by multiple pathogens. Examinations of snakes with SFD indicate that the fungus invades deeply into the epidermis and dermis, hence molting may not rid the animal of infection despite temporary resolution of clinical signs. The significance of SFD in free-ranging snakes is also currently under investigation. As the name of the disease implies, SFD is only known to affect snakes.

Human Health Considerations: None

Disease Control and Biosecurity: Wear clean disposable gloves when handling sick or dead snakes. Clean supplies and field equipment with soap and water followed by disinfection with a 10% bleach solution (9 part water, 1 part bleach) between animals and sites. When SFD is already known to occur in a region, snakes whose skin lesions appear to resolve with supportive care and/or antifungal therapy may be candidates for release at their capture site, but these individuals should not be released in an area where the disease has not been previously as it is not known if treated snakes may still harbor viable fungus.

Please continue to monitor this mortality event and provide periodic updates to NWHC Epidemiology Team throughout the course of the event as additional considerations and further investigation may be warranted.

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Valerie I. Shearn-Bochsler

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The USGS-National Wildlife Health Center conducts wildlife disease investigations with state, federal and tribal partners, and we welcome collaborative dissemination of this information (e.g., publication, press release, technical report, etc.). Please contact the pathologist or wildlife disease epidemiologist assigned to this case to ensure that information is accurately interpreted and appropriately credited.

Copies To:

BOB DITTMAR

Texas Parks & Wildlife Department, 1620 FM 2218, Richmond, TX 77469

CLAYTON WOLF

Texas Parks & Wildlife/Austin, 4200 Smith School Road, Austin, TX 78744

This is a Report for your submission to the National Wildlife Health Center.

For consultation regarding diagnostic findings or laboratory testing and results, please contact the pathologist. Contact information can be found underneath the signature line on this report.

For consultation on the significance of this disease to wildlife populations in your area, assistance with disease control and response, or to report field updates (numbers and species affected, geographical distribution, end date, etc.), please contact an NWHC epidemiologist at NWHC-epi@usgs.gov or 608-270-2480.